

Case Report

Childhood Conundrum: A Rare Encounter with Myoepithelial Carcinoma of the Parotid Gland in an 8-Year-Old Girl

Dr. Prathibha R © 2025 by the author's. The terms and conditions of the Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY) license apply to this open access article.**1. Introduction**

Myoepithelial carcinoma of the parotid gland constitutes less than 5% of all salivary gland tumors [1]. In the pediatric population, salivary gland neoplasms are uncommon with an incidence of approximately 3–4 per 10,000 cases accounting for less than 5% of salivary gland tumors and under 2% of all head and neck neoplasms [2]. The diagnosis of these tumors remains challenging due to their rarity and wide histological variability which significantly impact clinical prognosis. Since 1991, the World Health Organization (WHO) has classified myoepithelial carcinoma as a distinct subtype of salivary gland tumors [3]. Here, we report a rare case of myoepithelial carcinoma in the parotid gland of an 8-year-old girl, notable for its extensive invasion of the facial nerve.

2. Case Presentation

An 8-year-old girl came to the hospital with swelling just below the right ear lobe, which her parents had first noticed a few months ago. At the beginning, it was not bigger than a pea and it was painless and slow-growing. Over time, however, it steadily increased in size, eventually reaching about 4 × 3 cm.

Concerned about the gradual progression, the child underwent radiological evaluation. An ultrasound of the neck revealed a large, ill-defined hypoechoic soft tissue mass within the right parotid gland. Multiple calcifications were noted within the lesion, which measured approximately $3.8 \times 3.7 \times 2.7$ cm.

To gain further clarity, a Contrast-Enhanced Computed Tomography (CECT) scan of neck was performed. The scan showed an irregular soft tissue density lesion measuring around 42×37 mm, involving the right parotid gland, again with coarse calcifications seen within it. On post-contrast imaging, the mass demonstrated heterogeneous enhancement, raising strong suspicion for a neoplastic process.

To further investigate the nature of lesion, Fine-Needle Aspiration Cytology (FNAC) was performed.

Fine-needle aspiration showed benign cells in the form of ductal cells and myoepithelial cells. These cells are arranged in cohesive clusters, few in sheets in singles. Background shows chondromyxoid stroma. Which yielded the diagnosis of pleomorphic adenoma?. Figure 1 followed by which patient underwent radical parotidectomy with supra-omohyoid neck dissection with right lateral tarsorrhaphy and the resected specimen was initially sent for frozen section which revealed tumor cells arranged in nests and lobules. These tumor cells are highly pleomorphic with high nuclear to cytoplasmic ratio and scant cytoplasm. Also seen are areas of central necrosis was noted. Impression of salivary duct carcinoma was given. Gross specimen of enlarged parotid gland with irregular grey white lesion ($8 \times 3.5 \times 2.2$ cm) showing areas of calcification and necrosis on cut surface 2.

Figure 1: Smear showing benign ductal cells and myoepithelial cells in clusters and chondromyxoid stroma background

Figure 2: Gross image showing cut section of parotid swelling with areas of calcification

Microscopy-Tumor cells are arranged in nests and lobular pattern. Tumor cells are highly pleomorphic having indistinct cell borders with round nuclei, prominent nucleoli and moderate amount of cytoplasm. These nests of tumor cells show comedo-necrosis and are seen invading into the adjacent stroma showing desmoplastic reaction. Hence a diagnosis of salivary duct carcinoma was given Figure 3 and 4.

Immunohistochemistry revealed that the tumor cells expressed positivity for cytokeratin, S100, calponin, P40, P63 and S100. This pattern of immunostaining is consistent with diagnosis of Myoepithelial Carcinoma Figure 5.

Figure 3: Microscopy H&E (10X) showing tumor cells arranged in nests separated by fibrous septa

Figure 4: Microscopy H&E (40X) showing individual cells with prominent nucleoli and black arrow showing comedo-necrosis

Figure 5: Immunostaining showing positivity for S100 (subset-nuclear staining)

3. Discussion

Salivary gland tumors are uncommon in children. They consist of variable histopathological subtypes of benign and malignant tumors [3]. Most often 85% of salivary gland malignancies in children occur in the parotid gland [4]. If a firm parotid mass in a child should always raise the suspicion of malignancy. Myoepithelial carcinoma (MC) typically presents as a painless swelling, but often with additional symptoms that distinguish it from benign tumors [5]. The symptoms may include prolonged evolution, rapid growth, pain (10-29%), facial paralysis (10-15%), numbness or tingling in the tongue or lips, difficulty in swallowing, a hard or stone-like consistency, fixation to surrounding structures, and abnormal lymphadenopathy [6].

Myoepitheliomas represent roughly 1% of the entire subset of parotid tumors which may arise de novo or within a pleomorphic adenoma [7]. In contrast, the incidence of these tumors in children is unclear, but it's believed that benign and malignant cases occur at a similar rate. The average age of diagnosis in pediatric cases is 16 years [8]. In our case the age of the patient is 8 years. Despite its low-grade nature, the MC has a significant local recurrence rate of 42% and a 10% rate of lymph node metastasis. Complete surgical removal through parotidectomy is the preferred treatment [9].

Fine-Needle Aspiration (FNA) is a minimally invasive procedure, citing minimal discomfort done without general anesthesia. FNA allows for rapid diagnosis and obviates the need for open biopsy. In cases of inconclusive FNA, superficial parotidectomy with facial nerve sparing is the recommended minimal procedure for diagnosis and treatment of a solitary parotid mass [10]. Most myoepithelial carcinomas arise from pleomorphic adenomas, previously classified as mixed tumors, and are typically low-grade malignancies [11]. However, when they occur in isolation or de novo, they are often high-grade carcinomas. This highlights the importance of careful diagnosis and evaluation of these rare tumors in children. Myoepithelial carcinoma (MC) exhibits aggressive behavior with local recurrence rates ranging from 46.1-51.9%, and overall survival rates are 78% at 2 years and 71-78% at 5 years [2].

The diagnostic sequence goes like conventional FNAC was reported as pleomorphic adenoma because of cellular atypia in Giemsa stain. Frozen/HPE reported as salivary duct carcinoma, IHC finally supporting myoepithelial carcinoma (MC) is most likely explained by a combination of sampling limitations, intratumoural heterogeneity and morphologic overlap between salivary tumours. On FNA the presence of ductal cells, myoepithelial-appearing cells and chondromyxoid stroma is entirely consistent with pleomorphic adenoma or a lesion with pleomorphic-adenoma-like areas; cytology therefore can under call malignant transformation or a high-grade myoepithelial phenotype if the aspirate samples primarily the benign component. The frozen section and routine (H&E) showed highly pleomorphic nests with comedo-type necrosis, perineural invasion and desmoplastic reaction - features that mimic high-grade entities such as salivary duct carcinoma (SDC) or mucoepidermoid carcinoma and can lead to an SDC impression on morphology alone. IHC resolved the dilemma by demonstrating myoepithelial differentiation (positivity for cytokeratin, S100, calponin, p40/p63), supporting myoepithelial carcinoma rather than SDC. Thus, the sequence reflects sampling bias (FNA), morphologic mimicry (H&E) and the diagnostic value of lineage-specific immunomarkers (IHC).

These findings were supported by a study done by Cormier et al in 2021 describing a patient whose initial diagnosis was pleomorphic adenoma on FNA but on recurrence and excision it was found to have myoepithelial carcinoma ex-pleomorphic adenoma with IHC positive for S100 and p63 clarifying the diagnosis [12].

These findings indicate that MC is a more aggressive tumor than previously thought, with a significant risk of metastasis and recurrence. After thorough literature search our case was found to be the first case report where there is occurrence of Myoepithelial carcinoma of parotid gland in an 8-year-old girl.

4. Conclusion

Myoepithelial carcinoma (MC) has been reported in young children in very few studies, highlighting the importance of considering this diagnosis in unexpected populations. A high index of suspicion is crucial when evaluating a parotid gland mass in children. Accurate histopathological examination is essential to identify features indicative of aggressive behavior in MC. Also the IHC an ancillary technique which aided in the diagnostic challenge.

Statement of Declaration

We declare that the manuscript has been read and approved by all the authors, that the requirements for authorship have been met, and that each author believes that the manuscript represents honest work.

All authors contributed to the study conception and design. Material preparation, data collection and analysis were performed by Dr. Prathibha R and Dr. T.N.Suresh. The first draft of the manuscript was written by Dr. Prathibha R and all authors commented on previous versions of the manuscript. All authors read and approved the final manuscript.

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